

Karakul breeding prospects of genomic selection

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ABSTRACT

The conditions of the steppe pastures of Kyzylkum created opportunities for breeding colored karakul sheep. In particular, types of pedigree karakul related to the Bukhara sur were bred. However, such types of Bukhara sur as gold, silver and diamond do not yet have a brand on the world market. Our goal is to form a select herd of karakul sheep and create a line of pedigree breeders. In Uzbekistan, which is considered the birthplace of karakul, a favorable economic environment has been created for processing and manufacturing finished products.

Keywords

DNA diagnostics, The creation of a biotechnological laboratory will enrich the scientific infrastructure, including for studying the genome of livestock in such steppe zones of Uzbekistan as the Bukhara region and the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

When assessing the productivity of farm animals, it is impossible to do without the use of modern biotechnological methods. Therefore, the development and implementation of gene diagnostic methods (DNA diagnostics) in animal husbandry are an urgent task of fundamental and applied biotechnology. The Navoi branch of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan is completing the implementation of an applied project aimed at creating a universal biotechnological laboratory in animal husbandry and developing gene diagnostic methods based on the study of the genome of Karakul sheep. The newspaper's correspondent talked with the head of this project, candidate of agricultural sciences, senior researcher of the Navoi branch of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan Uktam Khakimov. DNA diagnostics is a form of genome analysis. Its main task is to identify polymorphic variants of genes. Usually, when evaluating farm animals, phenotypic characteristics are used. Using genome analysis increases the accuracy and completeness of selection and breeding work. In the selection of Karakul sheep, their color and color types are the main phenotypic characteristics. Studying the genome of Karakul sheep and using genome analysis in their selection, along with reducing the time of selection processes, increase the accuracy of forecasting. Our project is aimed at enriching DNA diagnostics with methods of individual phenotypic assessment of Karakul stud rams, including for improving selection methods. Thus, methods for assessing the import and export of breeding cattle will be developed based on DNA analysis. The object of our research was Istiklol LLC, which specializes in Karakul breeding, with which the Navoi branch of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan has an agreement on scientific cooperation. This farm breeds black sheep, Bukhara and Karakalpak sur. These are mainly young (under 40) researchers, including independent researchers, doctoral students and interns, who collect and analyze blood samples from Karakul sheep and prepare relevant reports on the results of the work. It should be noted that a scientific laboratory and infrastructure facilities were

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organized at the Navoi branch of the Academy of Sciences to implement the project and equipped with the necessary equipment. The creation of a biotechnology laboratory will enrich the scientific infrastructure, including for studying the genome of livestock in such steppe zones of Uzbekistan as the Bukhara region and the Republic of Karakalpakstan. According to statistics, more than half of the total number of Karakul sheep among the regions of the country is in the Navoi region. By the way, the research staff of our department got acquainted with the methodology for conducting molecular genetic analyses, which are carried out in the biotechnology laboratories of the Center for Genomics and Bioinformatics and the Institute of Zoology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In general, practical and fundamental projects on studying the genome and developing methods for genetic diagnostics of livestock have not been carried out by our scientists before. Such research has been carried out by foreign researchers over the past 15-20 years. For example, Russian scientists carried out molecular genetic diagnostics of farm animals, and their colleagues from Iran studied the genomes of Karakul sheep. The use of molecular genetic methods is of great importance in livestock breeding. In the development of animal husbandry, without the introduction of modern biotechnological methods, it is impossible to give a full assessment of the defining features of

livestock productivity, since today only phenotypic features are taken into account in the assessment of farm animals. Meanwhile, breeding information on the transmission of features from generation to generation is contained in the DNA molecules of farm animals. This circumstance determines the relevance of the problem of introducing fundamental and applied biotechnology. The conditions of the steppe pastures of Kyzylkum created opportunities for breeding colored Karakul sheep. In particular, the types of breeding

Karakul sheep have been bred

There are no competitive varieties of astrakhan. In our country, in addition to black and gray colors, white fleece and "candle flame" are produced. Currently, in karakul breeding, selection and selection of karakul sheep of different colors and astrakhan types of shades are carried out based on traditional methods (Mendel). Selection and breeding work in domestic karakul breeding is organized in specialized farms. At the same time, in the selection of karakul sheep, the factory type of small cattle as a result of many years of selection work is considered an achievement. In our genodiagnostic laboratory, the genomes of 2-2.5 thousand heads of breeding rams will be studied and evaluated annually. In terms of distribution and quantity, breeding karakul sheep occupy positions in the top ten among more than 500 breeds of sheep in the world. And not only because of the karakul, but also

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due to biological and genetic characteristics. Today, Karakul sheep are bred in more than 20 countries around the world. However, the number of countries exporting Karakul astrakhan fur does not exceed five or six. These are mainly Uzbekistan, Afghanistan, Namibia and Turkmenistan. Breeding selection work on Karakul sheep is also practiced in Germany, the USA, Romania, Kazakhstan, Iran and China, where scientific research work on DNA diagnostics of sheep is well organized. I repeat, the correct organization of selection of farm animals is important for increasing their productivity. At the same time, it is impossible to develop livestock farming using traditional selection methods without the introduction of biotechnological methods. In countries where Karakul breeding is not an economic sphere, the genome of Karakul sheep has been studied as an experimental object. In Uzbekistan, this is an entire agricultural sector. In addition, there are many livestock breeders, as well as specialists in processing Karakul, interested in the productivity of Karakul sheep. The main thing is that it can be used for many years to develop pasture livestock farming. To create a universal scientific platform within the walls of the Navoi branch of the Academy of Sciences, certain intellectual knowledge and skills were required. A sufficient level of scientific potential has been formed among the scientists of the department in the field of agriculture and biology. It is also worth considering that the Navoi branch of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan has established close cooperation with leading domestic scientific institutions, young researchers are working in the areas of chemistry and technology. This is a sufficient resource for the full functioning of the laboratory. In order to strengthen the research work carried out here, it is necessary to further improve the qualifications of its employees and laboratory assistants in the field of biotechnology, including on the basis of the Center for Genomics and Bioinformatics of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Center for Advanced Technologies under the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and to undergo internships in research centers. The difference between the zoobiotechnology laboratory created and similar domestic ones is that its activities will be more focused on the study of farm animals, while research work in biotechnological research centers and laboratories of the republic is mainly aimed at studying plants and microorganisms. Meanwhile, fundamental and practical research in the field of zoobiotechnology has been conducted in developed countries for 10-15 years. As in any research activity, experiments in animal husbandry, in particular, in the study of the genome in karakul breeding and the development of gene diagnostics methods are associated with unexpected difficulties, positive and negative results. Scientists of the Navoi branch of the Academy of Sciences are considering the prospects of genomic selection in karakul breeding for the next two years from the point of view of creating a selection technology based on the genetics of pigmentation of colored karakul sheep. This is the second practical project, which is currently under consideration by the Ministry of Innovative Development. The scientific laboratory at the Navoi branch will become the basis for future research. The gene pool will be formed from the breeding herd of the Scientific Research Experimental Station "Kyzylkum" as part of the Navoi branch of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan together with partners - LLC "Istiklol" and "Nurata", specializing in karakul breeding.

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